

GEO MORPHOMETRY
PERUGIA ITALY

2025
JUNE 9-13

Multidisciplinary Application of Geomorphometry for the Characterization of the Northern Gulf of Mexico Seafloor, United States

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Abstract—Geomorphometry is now commonly applied to the study of the marine environment. Here, we present a case study in which multiple disciplinary approaches were integrated with geomorphometry to characterise the northern Gulf of Mexico. A digital bathymetric model spanning 233,000 km² and built from 3D seismic data was combined with a smaller bathymetric dataset collected using a multibeam echosounder. Using different software (*e.g.*, R, WhiteboxTools, ArcGIS Pro), terrain variables were derived and submarine landforms were extracted from these datasets. These derivatives were then integrated with other environmental variables to delineate and characterise pockmarks, predict the mean grain size of seafloor substrate, constrain and characterise a submarine landslide, and predict cold-water coral distribution in parts of the Gulf of Mexico. In an area north of the Sigsbee Escarpment, a total of 4,017 pockmarks were delineated. In the area covered by the multibeam data, the range of mean grain size was predicted to be between -0.23 and 6.29 phi (average of 1.12 phi). Important predictor variables included a broad-scale bathymetric position index, mean and standard deviation of bathymetry, and the vector ruggedness measure (VRM). The characterization of a submarine landslide using geomorphometry showed that variations in terrain variables can efficiently demarcate the headwall, but the lateral extent of the landslide toe is more challenging to define, although the integration of a submarine landform classification helped delineate it. Finally, the

ensemble model of cold-water corals enabled the identification of 3,888 km² of suitable habitat. Primary predictors included bathymetry, VRM, and slope. These results highlight the potential of geomorphometry to contribute to multidisciplinary environmental studies in the marine realm, which can tell us about seafloor environments' past, present, and future conditions and can be used to inform resource management, conservation, or restoration.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last decade since [1], the applications of geomorphometry to the marine realm have increased dramatically. More marine scientists are now aware of geomorphometry as a science, which facilitated the adaptation of terrestrial geomorphometric approaches to the specificities of underwater studies and the development of new approaches specific to marine terrain [2-4]. As new marine disciplines adopt geomorphometry to expand their analytical potential, it becomes interesting and relevant to conduct multidisciplinary characterization of areas to understand better how they evolved through time, which natural processes are influenced by their geomorphology, and how they might change in the future under various impacts from anthropogenic activities and climate change. Here, we used digital

surface models of the northern Gulf of Mexico to conduct such a multidisciplinary characterization anchored in geomorphometry, including approaches from marine geology, geomorphology, biology, and ecology.

II. METHODS

A. Data

Two digital bathymetric models were used. First, the northern Gulf of Mexico deepwater bathymetry grid built from 3D seismic data and provided by the United States Bureau of Ocean Energy Management [5] was downloaded at its native resolution of 12 m. This dataset spans approximately 233,000 km², with depths ranging from 39 to 3380 m deep (Fig. 1). It shows a relatively high diversity of geomorphic and geomorphological features.

Second, a digital bathymetric model produced with a Kongsberg Maritime EM 1002 multibeam echosounder and provided by the United States Geological Survey (USGS) was used (survey #W00609). The survey was performed in 2001 about 30 nautical miles south of Cape San Blas, in Florida. It has a resolution of 8 m and spans about 394 km² (Fig. 1).

The MultiscaleDTM R package [6] was used to derive 17 terrain variables (*e.g.*, slope, rugosity measures, curvatures) from the northern Gulf of Mexico dataset, both on the native 12 m resolution and on a resampled version of the dataset of 40 m

Figure 1. Northern Gulf of Mexico bathymetry grid at 40 m resolution with cold-water coral observations used for the species distribution modelling (top); digital bathymetric model produced from multibeam data with seabed sediment data used for mean grain size modelling (bottom left); and results of the mean grain size modelling (units: phi) (bottom right).

resolution – to facilitate the more computationally-intensive processes. A 3x3 window of analysis was used in both cases. Then, the multiscale capabilities of WhiteboxTools were harnessed to produce a multiscale roughness variable [7], derived using a search neighbourhood varying from 1 (3x3; analysis distance of 120 m) to 1001 (2,003 x 2,003; analysis distance of 80,12 km) and a step size of 1. For the multibeam dataset, common seafloor-surface variables used in marine habitat mapping were calculated in ArcGIS Pro using the Benthic Terrain Modeller toolbox [2]. These included slope, benthic position indices, and a vector ruggedness measure, among others, many with a window of analysis of 36 cells to account for the relative homogeneity of the area.

Seven types of morphometric features were also delineated using the MultiscaleDTM R package, at different window sizes (3x3, 9x9, 15x15, 21x21). The BRESS (Bathymetric and Reflectivity-based Segments) v.2.5.2 tool [3], which uses principles of topographic openness, pattern recognition, and texture classification to identify geomorphic elements of the seafloor, was also used using the default parameters. Four classification schemes were applied, each identifying either 4, 5, 6, or 10 types of landforms.

In terms of the other environmental variables used for the analyses, mean grain size measurements for a portion of the Gulf were obtained from the USGS usSEABED dataset [8]. This dataset is a compilation of seabed sediment data aggregated from multiple sources. Deep-sea coral occurrence data were retrieved from the United States National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration Deep-Sea Coral Data Portal. Data were filtered to include only coral observations associated with a positional accuracy of 20 m, so they spatially aligned with the 40 m resolution pixels of the bathymetry, which left 5,769 observations.

B. Pockmark Delineation and Characterization

The northwestern Gulf of Mexico north of the Sigsbee Escarpment is characterised by a distinctively deformed seafloor surface resulting from the upward migration and dissolution of deep salt deposits. As salt diapirs move up, sediments over them are uplifted creating seafloor doming structures, which are often cracked by a network of extensional faults that provide pathways for fluid and/or gas migration. When these emerge at the seafloor, they create circular or elongated depressions or craters, generally called pockmarks (*e.g.*, gas seeps or mud volcanoes), that often harbour unique ecosystems.

Here, we analysed a subset of the northern Gulf of Mexico dataset (5,135 km²) associated with some of these doming structures to map pockmarks. A semi-automated procedure enabled by the CoMMA toolbox for ArcGIS Pro [4] was utilised. First, a boundary-based delineation on a directional median derivative was applied to extract polygons using a window of analysis of 21 cells, and a geomorphons layer was produced. Statistics were calculated on both the boundary-delineated objects

and the geomorphons. Finally, a rule-based filtering was applied to retain only the polygons with specific characteristics linked to pockmarks.

C. Mean Grain Size Prediction

A number of potential substrate parameters can be mapped, such as sediment composition or presence/absence; here we focus on the mean grain size - a common metric that describes the average sediment grain diameter from a physical seabed sample. Using the multibeam dataset and its terrain derivatives, seafloor substrate patterns were mapped within an object-based image analysis (OBIA) framework. A multiresolution segmentation was applied on the terrain variables in Trimble eCognition v10.2, followed by a Grow region algorithm to merge objects with low rugosity. Objects were then further merged using a spectral difference segmentation. The final objects each contained information on the mean, standard deviation, GLCM homogeneity (all direction) and GLCM entropy (all direction) for all input layers.

Regression was used to model the mean grain size observed within each image object polygon as a function of the terrain variables. The average value of mean grain size measurements was calculated where multiple sediment samples occurred within a single polygon, resulting in 86 complete observations of predictor and response variables available for random forest modelling, which was conducted using the R package randomForest. After training, model diagnostics were investigated, and values of mean grain size were predicted over the entire extent of the multibeam dataset using the predictor values, and validation was conducted.

D. Submarine Landslide Characterisation

Landslide susceptibility at water depths greater than 120 m was modelled by Dyer *et al.* [9] using terrain variables in addition to other geomorphological, geological, and geochemical factors. Their results show that sediment type (mud, sand, gravel, or rock) and slope are the most important predictors of where a landslide will occur, although they note that the importance of slope might be overestimated as a consequence of steeper headwall scarps, which are left behind after failure [9]. To better understand these headwalls, we used the terrain variables derived from the 12 m resolution northern Gulf of Mexico dataset to characterise a specific submarine landslide and its different components quantitatively. The landslide was identified on the edge of the continental shelf in an area of high landslide probability based on the model by Dyer *et al.* [9].

E. Cold-Water Coral Distribution

An iterative ensemble species distribution modelling approach was implemented following Lecours *et al.* [10]. In short, correlations were measured between the 40 m resolution bathymetry and all terrain variables derived from it. Uncorrelated variables were then combined with the coral observation data in

the SSDM R package. A geographic resampling was applied to coral occurrences to ensure that no two observations were found in the same pixel so that the importance of the environmental conditions at that location was not artificially amplified. This reduced the number of observations for the modelling to 1,706. Nine different modelling techniques were combined into the ensemble model: generalized linear models (GLM), generalized additive models (GAM), multivariate adaptive regression splines (MARS), classification tree analysis (CTA), generalized boosted models (GBM), maximum entropy (MaxEnt), artificial neural networks (ANN), random forests (RF) and support vector machines (SVM). All parameters used to run the model can be found in Lecours *et al.* [10], with the only difference being that the 10-fold validation method was conducted with only one cross-validation and that the threshold for model selection as part of the ensemble was based solely on the area under the curve (AUC) of the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve, which had to be greater than 0.75. Results of this first model were analyzed, and the model was rerun using only the variables that contributed more than 5% to the model.

III. RESULTS

A. Terrain Characterisation

The various terrain variables derived from the bathymetry show a high geomorphometric diversity, hinting at the different geological processes that formed them. The multiscale roughness analysis clearly identified some of the known features in the area with higher values, such as the West Florida Escarpment, the Keathley Canyon, the slopes of the Mississippi Canyon, and the edges of many salt domes. Dominant scales for roughness were identified at 7x7 (280 m by 280 m), 87x87 (3.48 km), and 111x111 (4.44 km), among others. The different characterizations of morphometric features identified that the area is mainly composed of flat areas and slopes, with a significant number of channels and ridges depending on the scale of analysis.

Figure 2. Subset of the northern Gulf of Mexico dataset showing the delineated pockmarks (purple polygons), and the areas identified as suitable for cold-water corals (black pixels). Background bathymetry ranges from about 230 m deep (in red) to 475 m deep (in dark purple).

B. Pockmark Delineation and Characterization

A total of 4,017 pockmarks were delineated in the sub-area studied. The pits form within faults (elongated depressions) or are independent, single structures (about 44% of the pockmarks). Some of these single pockmarks were as deep as 40 m. At many places, trains of pockmarks coalesce to create thin, elongated features (~400 instances), potentially indicating a buried fault that has not breached the surface. There appears to be no correlation between depth and structure type, suggesting that similar processes occur throughout the region. The pockmarks align closely with the valleys and pits identified by the BRESS tool (Fig. 2).

C. Mean Grain Size Prediction

The mean grain size predictions are presented in Fig. 1. The R^2 statistic from the cross-validation suggested that the predictions explained about 61% of the variance of the ground-truthed observations. Results suggested that the mean broad-scale BPI was the most important predictor variable, followed by the mean bathymetry of each image object, the standard deviation of bathymetry, and the mean VRM. All other predictors contributed less than 10% to the model's predictive capacity.

D. Submarine Landslide Characterisation

While the headwall of the submarine landslide was clearly demarcated by variations in the value of most terrain variables, they must be considered together to fully understand the boundaries of the submarine landslide. The lateral extent of the landslide toe was more challenging to define, but can be constrained using northness in combination with the morphometric feature classification. Small variations at the toe are also visible in the plots of relative position variables, the roughness index elevation (RIE), and minimum curvature. The morphometric features characterization highlighted the two-part nature of the landslide: the eroded headwall region, where the slope is incised by channels that drain towards the centre of the headwall; and the translational body of the landslide, characterised by ridges and channels, and slope-parallel compressional ridges at the toe.

E. Cold-Water Coral Distribution

The uncorrelated variables included in the first model were bathymetry, slope, easternness, northernness, topographic position index, vector ruggedness measure (VRM), and maximum, minimum, plan, and twist curvatures. After the first model was run, only bathymetry, VRM, and slope were deemed to contribute enough to the predictions to be retained for the final model, which identified approximately 3,888 km² of suitable habitat (>70% of probability of occurrence) for cold-water corals. However, based on the evaluation metrics, the model's performance was only fair. Bathymetry remained the primary driver of coral distribution, followed by VRM and slope. Despite corals being found at all depths, predicted coral distribution generally aligns closely with broad-scale topographic highs in relatively shallower waters, and

with finer-scale topographic lows such as valleys and pits identified by the submarine landform classifications and the delineated pockmarks (Fig. 2).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

These examples of applications of marine geomorphometry show the benefits of multidisciplinary efforts. Without combining the different analyses, we would not know that some valleys and pits identified by submarine landform classifications correspond to pockmarks that may have been formed by gas seeping through the seafloor, which create suitable habitat for cold-water corals. They also demonstrate the potential of a single data type, digital bathymetric models, to provide relevant information about dynamic and complex marine systems. With the increased interest in marine resources, it becomes critical to map and comprehensively characterize seafloor environments to inform decision-making in several contexts.

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